
95. Our Galaxy’s tumbling disk

I WILL LOOK AT two large-scale dynamical phenomena which are, today, believed to affect the bulk motion of our Galaxy’s disk with respect to its dark matter halo.

The first, not yet observed, but tied to their primordial origin, would be a remarkable confirmation of one of the predictions of the cosmological Λ CDM structure formation paradigm. The other, related to the orbit of our neighbouring Large Magellanic Cloud, results in a huge disk perturbation which has recently been measured using the astrometric data in Gaia Data Release 2.

IN THE DECADE or so preceding the launch of Gaia, the simple view in which our Galaxy’s disk is fixed in orientation within a spherical dark matter halo was being challenged by a number of studies and simulations.

It seemed increasingly inevitable that the disk–halo orientation is likely to vary with time, due to effects including the infall of misaligned gas (Binney & May, 1986; Roskar et al., 2010), and the tidal effects of the Large Magellanic Cloud (Weinberg & Blitz, 2006). These tidal effects presumably extend to ancient infall satellites and their associated debris (e.g. Dodge et al., 2022).

Meanwhile, simulations also showed that, in galaxies more generally, the inner disk and outer halo often decouple, with average misalignments of $30 - 40^\circ$.

OTHER COMPLICATIONS were also becoming evident. Amongst these, simulations of galaxy formation were predicting that most galaxy halos ‘tumble’, in inertial space, with a typical rotation rate of around 2 radians per Hubble time (Bailin & Steinmetz, 2004).

Analytical arguments (e.g. Nelson & Tremaine, 1995), and numerical simulations (Dubinski & Kuijken, 1995), furthermore suggested that dynamical friction in the inner galaxy regions should couple the inner disk to the halo, at least within the region dominated by baryons rather than dark matter (Bailin & Steinmetz, 2004).

It follows that, if the angular momentum vectors of the disk and halo remain coupled, the plane defined by the disk stars should rotate at some $30 \mu\text{arcsec yr}^{-1}$ with respect to the quasar reference frame.

In 2014, with colleagues David Spergel and Lennart Lindegren, I looked at the detectability, with Gaia, of a time-varying orientation of our Galaxy’s disk with respect to its dark matter halo (Perryman et al., 2014). Our simulations suggested that any residual rotation of the Gaia reference frame with respect to a truly inertial reference system (approximated to by observable quasars) should be at the level of some $0.2 - 0.5 \mu\text{arcsec yr}^{-1}$.

Although we must await future Gaia results for confirmation, this accuracy of the reference frame should, in due course, allow for the detection of such a cosmological ‘tumbling’ motion of our own Galaxy’s disk.

It has since been shown, from cosmological hydrodynamical simulations, that the same effect may be detectable in other Local Group galaxies. For example, Earp et al. (2019) found average tilting rates for their sample of $3.8 \pm 2.3^\circ \text{Gyr}^{-1}$, compared to a detection limit of some $0.27^\circ \text{Gyr}^{-1}$.

IS THERE any evidence that our Galaxy’s disk is tilted with respect to a (non-spherical) dark matter halo? One such example, also advanced by Gaia, is provided by two significant stellar ‘overdensities’ in the outer halo: the Virgo stellar stream, or Virgo Overdensity, discovered in 2006 (Duffau et al., 2006), and the Hercules–Aquila Cloud, discovered in 2007 (Belokurov et al., 2007).

Han et al. (2022) found that the debris from the Gaia–Enceladus merger, some 8–10 Gyr ago, and discovered in the Gaia data (essay #15), can be associated with these overdensities only if the halo potential is tilted, while orbit integration within a *spherical* halo would result in the rapid phase mixing of any initial asymmetries. In their tilted model, the Hercules–Aquila Cloud and the Virgo Overdensity arise as ‘apocentric pile-ups’ of the merger debris, which then persist in space over many Gyr.

They concluded that a coherent picture is now emerging, in which the Galaxy’s stellar halo out to 30 kpc is dominated by debris from this ancient radial merger, which is itself globally asymmetric, and demarcated by the two apocentres of the Virgo Overdensity (above the disk), and Hercules–Aquila Cloud (below the disk).

Further support for this picture, also coming from the Gaia DR2 data, is the fact that these features occupy opposing octants of the Galaxy, overlap in orbit properties, and exhibit metallicity distributions indistinguishable from that of Gaia–Enceladus.

More specifically, Iorio & Belokurov (2019) used the DR2 data to construct slices parallel to the Milky Way disk, showing that within 30 kpc from the Galactic centre the halo is triaxial, with the longest axis misaligned by $\sim 70^\circ$ with respect to the Galactic x -axis. The procedure again exposed the large diffuse overdensities, identified with the Hercules–Aquila Cloud and the Virgo overdensity, and aligned with the semi-major axis of the halo.

Furthermore, they constructed the kinematics of the inner halo by mapping the proper motions of high-luminosity RR Lyrae stars, demonstrating that the inner halo is dominated by stars on highly eccentric orbits, with pericentres around 1 kpc and apocentres at 15–25 kpc from the Galactic centre (Simion et al., 2019).

FOR THE REMAINDER of this essay, I will explore the other effect on our Galaxy's disk that I mentioned at the start: the consequences of the existence of the Large Magellanic Cloud. First, we need some background.

High-precision proper motions of stars in the Large and Small Magellanic Clouds made with the Hubble Space Telescope around 2006, suggested transverse velocities of ~ 200 – 300 km s^{-1} , and led to orbit solutions suggesting that the Clouds are either on only their first infall about the Milky Way, or are on an eccentric long-period orbit of more than 6 Gyr (Kallivayalil et al., 2013).

Gómez et al. (2015) demonstrated that previous estimates of the Large Magellanic Cloud's orbital period and apocentric distance derived assuming a *fixed* Milky Way are significantly shortened in models where the Milky Way moves freely in response to the gravitational attraction of the LMC, and that the probability of models favouring a first infall is accordingly reduced. Including this interaction, they found that the Milky Way centre of mass within the inner 50 kpc can be significantly displaced, by as much as 30 kpc in position and 75 km s^{-1} in velocity, over time scales of only 0.3–0.5 Gyr.

Garavito-Camargo et al. (2019) used numerical simulations to explore the expected consequences as these satellite galaxies orbit within the dark matter halos of their hosts. For example, they found that the Large Magellanic Cloud should generate a pronounced trailing 'wake', in both the stellar and dark matter halos, leading to overdensities and distinct kinematic patterns that should be observable with Gaia.

Further numerical simulations by Petersen & Peñarrubia (2020) confirmed that the Milky Way disk may be moving at 40 km s^{-1} relative to the barycentre prior to the Large Magellanic Cloud infall, dislodging the Milky Way disk from the Galaxy's centre of mass in the process.

WITH THIS BACKGROUND it should come as no surprise that, as the most massive satellite galaxy of the Milky Way, and just past its closest approach of about 50 kpc, and moving at more than 300 km s^{-1} , the LMC is likely to affect our Galaxy in a number of ways.

Petersen & Peñarrubia (2021) have quantified these effects using three classes of distant tracer objects: 543 K giants and 292 blue horizontal branch stars, selected from and with radial velocities determined by SDSS–SEGUE, and with distances and proper motions from Gaia DR2, along with 33 satellite galaxies with suitably determined orbits, again constrained by Gaia.

They found that the Milky Way disk is moving with respect to these various stellar tracers in the outer halo (at distances of 40–120 kpc) at a velocity of $32 \pm 4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, in the Galactic coordinate direction $l = 56 \pm 9^\circ$, $b = -34 \pm 10^\circ$. Interestingly, this direction points not towards the present-day location of

the LMC, but rather to an earlier location on its orbital trajectory. This is a consequence of the fact that the distant tracers have long dynamical times, and are thus slow to react to the LMC's gravitational pull. The result is that the Milky Way disk moves in response to the LMC while the outer halo does not; in other words the distant halo appears to move relative to the Milky Way disk.

The significant reflex motion, and the location of the apex, is consistent with a massive Large Magellanic Cloud falling in for the first time. Its magnitude is also consistent with numerical models where the infall mass is greater than about $10^{11} M_\odot$. Being significantly larger than the mass enclosed within its luminous radius, $\sim 1.7 \times 10^{10} M_\odot$, suggests that the infalling LMC was surrounded by an extended dark matter halo.

THEIR RESULTS indicate that dynamical models of our Galaxy cannot neglect the perturbations induced by the LMC infall, nor can observations of the stellar halo be treated in a reference frame that doesn't correct for the disk's reflex motion.

And they pose a number of questions: what was the structure of the stellar and dark matter halos prior to its infall? What is the trajectory of the LMC since the start of its infall, and how did the dynamics of dark matter alter its path? Does the LMC lose its dark matter halo to tides, and where does the stripped dark matter end up in our Galaxy? And what are the implications for the dynamics of the Local Group more widely, including the orbit of our nearest massive neighbour, Andromeda?

Gaia DR3 will surely assist with some of the answers!